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IMPACT OF PRIME-TIME REVOLUTION ON RADIO
ADVERTISING IN BANGALORE CITY

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Abstract

Radio stations block certain programmed schedules to offer prime time slots to rake in extra revenue. Prime time is the day part (block of a day's programming schedule) with the most number of listeners and is generally where radio networks and local stations reap much of their advertising revenues. This paper aims at understanding minute aspects of consumer listenership patterns that strengthen radio advertising as a medium. It mainly helps us understand the prime time revolution, its history, why the radio industry went through a revolution and how today, prime time is one of the most sorted businesses across the globe in the media industry.

Keywords: prime time revolution, radio advertising, radio industry

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1. Introduction:

With time the number of radio stations has increased from about 100 in 1990 to 209 in 1997. Indian radio now has tremendous reach and presents the best option for low-cost programming. Listenership of Indian Radio has reached a plateau. At times the listenership has risen in certain urban areas due to the recent time allotment to private companies on five FM stations. Film and other popular music thus earn advertising revenues from Rs. 527 million in 1991-2 to Rs. 809 million in 1995-96.

The noticeable development in Indian radio has been the proper efforts that were taken to use radio for social change, like the state-supported radio rural forums for agricultural communication in the 1960s and promotion of adult literacy in the 1980s. The advent of regional radio in India popularized this medium even more. More recently NGOs have come together and initiated several broadcast programmes on women and legal rights, emergency contraception, and tele-serials that deal with social issues.

Local broadcasting, reflecting local issues of concern to the community is another development of Indian radio. Some communication experts believe that an increased and accelerated commercialization of radio will eventually cut down the costs of FM radio sets, thus making local radio even more available to the extreme rural areas of the country. Presently, radio broadcasting is done in 24 languages and 146 dialects all across India and there are 104 million radio households in the country, using approximately 111 million radio sets. Radio stations block certain programmed schedules to offer prime time slots to rake in extra revenue. Prime time is the day part (block of a day's programming schedule) with the most number of listeners and is generally where radio networks and local stations reap much of their advertising revenues.

2. Objectives:

- ✓ To ascertain if the industry sector and the demand for prime-time slots by companies are related. Ex: A company targeting working population might choose the prime time slot as compared to a traditional saree company, targeting housewives, which would prefer the after-noon time.

- ✓ To study if time-compressed speech nullifies the communication aspect of the advertisement.
- ✓ To analyze if advertisements on radio in general, are influential on the target consumer.

3. Statement of the Problem

The war for prime-time slots by companies is highly increasing due to the desire of reaching out to the target consumer. Also considering the fact that prime-time charges are really high, clients resort to 'time compressed speech' in advertisements. Often times, this does not serve the purpose of the advertiser. Due to the economic slowdown, clients have started choosing advertising mediums that have the biggest impact with the least cost.

4. Hypothesis-1

H_0 : The client's ad expenditure and his demand for prime-time slots are independent.

H_1 : The client's ad expenditure and his demand for prime-time slots are dependent.

Hypothesis-2

H_0 : Time compressed speech does not result in effective brand recall.

H_1 : Time compressed speech does result in effective brand recall.

Hypothesis-3

H_0 : Radio listenership does not exert high influence on consumer's buying decision

H_1 : Radio listenership does exert high influence on consumer's buying decision

5. Primary Data

Method Used: Questionnaire

Sample Size: 30 Clients and 100 radio listeners. (TOTAL=130)

Technique: Convenient sampling

Data collection: Phone, e-mail and Personal Interview.

5.1 Data Collection

- E-mails.
- Journals.
- Web Portals.

5.2 Method of Study: Exploratory form of research

Exploratory research is a type of research conducted because a problem has not been clearly defined.

5.3 Method of Questionnaire: Administered Questionnaire

5.4 Statistical tools used:-

Chi square test & Likert rating scale

6. Scope of the study:

- ✓ This study has been conducted with a sample size of 30 clients and 100 listeners.
- ✓ The area covered for the same is Bangalore City, Karnataka, India.
- ✓ The comparisons have been drawn however, with other cities of India showing a high growth in the same medium.
- ✓ The clients are from various backgrounds and the listeners range in the age group of 18-28.

7. Findings

- a. Clarity of content in the advertisement remains the most important aspect of an advertisement following that would be the number of times an advertisement is repeated that would have an impact and even better if they are humorous or witty ads that listeners don't have an aversion towards.
- b. Around 36-38% people strongly feel the ads must be concise and to the point and should not contain irrelevant or too many details. Some listeners tune in only for a little while and also said short ads are always an advantage since you can get more advantage if you are buying the slot time-wise.
- c. Celebrity voice imitations have become a cliché now, and most of the dialogues are extremely repetitive. So, they fail to register an individual essence in the listener's mind. Radio shows already host filler programmes with celebrity voices like radio One's: Bangalooru with Rajni Saru
- d. A large chunk of listeners said they were not sure if length of the ad would help in better brand recall.
- e. Most of them said, they remembered GRD jewelers advertisement that stressed on their location, fast track ads because of their fun element and they did not remember Wockhardt's lengthy advertisement for cancer awareness programme
- f. The ad medium that influences people the largest according to this survey is the OOH Media/ billboards and hoardings. This is true in case of business travelers and also because more and more clients are avoiding TV due to its high cost.
- g. TV ads with 23% record the 2nd highest and the traditional mode of Word of Mouth advertising works the best for them, since the trust factor matters a lot. Direct marketing is a passé with only 14% of the people opting for it.
- h. We can notice that radio ads influence only 17% of the listeners compared to the other mediums. Hence, Radio ads must be complemented with ads placed in other mediums.
- i. Only 5% people said fashion updates would motivate them to listen to radio during prime hours.
- j. 17% people said since they would want to listen to national and international news updates during the prime time shows.

- k. A large chunk of them said 47% would love to be a part of interactive games with attractive gifts being given away. Since the prime time according to this survey falls in the evening largely, these games will sure be a huge crowd puller.
- l. The rest of the 31% said they would love to listen to personal interviews done with credible people in a very interesting manner with celebrities, socialites, ministers, CEOs, sportsmen or general public who have performed an extraordinary task.

8. Suggestions

1. Customers do not accept time-compressed speech as an effective format. To remove this aversion, the time compressed format can be improved.
2. Broadcasters can speak more rapidly. To facilitate the rapid speech it may be desirable to use two announcers, one quickly following up on the other's remarks. This is a technique frequently employed in sports broadcasting and it has the effect of creating a fast-paced information flow and an atmosphere of excitement.
3. The faster commercials should be substantially more interesting and, probably due to increased attention, they will be considerably better remembered. Since they are more interesting, they would probably be more effective in holding listener attention when radio is being listened to as a casual, companionable medium.
4. Some of the products being advertised, like real estate, institutions etc have gathered a very poor response when it comes to preference and brand recall of the listeners. This can be overcome by ensuring the 'right' placement of the ad since it may not be possible to compare humorous and serious ads together when they are played one after the other. Variations in these factors should be kept as small as practical.

9. Conclusion

Internationally, radio comprises seven to 15 per cent of the overall advertising pie. In India, this number varies from three to 3.5 per cent (approximately INR 500-550 crores) which clearly shows the potential of business yet to be explored. This bodes very well indeed for an industry which is seeing daybreak through growth and a robust measurement system like RAM which justifies the revenues spent, to advertisers.

Today, we have figures and facts which support what evangelists of the medium have been saying for a long time. It is a medium which delivers great RoI, has a very attractive cost per thousand (CPT) and is able to deliver not only frequency but a national reach for a brand builder. But more importantly, this is something no amount of media calculations will be ever able to do justice to-is the fact that because of the personal connect and one-on-one interactions with listeners, FM radio is able to touch their hearts and minds with far more impact than any other medium can ever do.

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